

REMEDIAL READING STRATEGY: AN ENHANCEMENT FOR READING COMPREHENSION AMONG GRADE 2 PUPILS

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Remedial Reading Strategy: An Enhancement for Reading Comprehension among Grade 2 Pupils

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Abstract

The study attempted to determine the extent of teachers' remedial reading program; the pupils' reading comprehension level; and the relationship between teachers' remedial reading program and pupils' reading comprehension level. The Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was employed in conjunction with the descriptive-correlational research approach to determine the significant link between the teachers' remedial reading program and the students' reading comprehension. The amount of remedial reading that teachers did and the reading comprehension level of their students were analyzed using the following statistical tools: mean, frequency count, standard deviation, and percentages. Findings revealed that teachers conducted "most of the time" remedial reading to their pupils as evidenced by the overall mean of 3.97 and standard deviation of .483. It was also revealed that out of 122 pupils, 37 or 30% were proficient readers while only 12 or (10%) were emerging readers. This implies that there are more proficient readers in the select public elementary schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City. Additionally, as seen by the computed ($r=.002$) and probability (.807) values, the results demonstrated that there was no significant association between the remedial reading program that teachers utilized and the students' reading comprehension. As a result, the null hypothesis is approved. Subsequently, it was recommended that in order to intensify pupils' reading comprehension, teachers should develop engaging learning materials which develop reading comprehension in English should be developed.

Keywords: remedial reading, pupils' reading comprehension, catch-up friday

Introduction

The groundwork in reading and writing has been the basis of the Department of Education (DepEd) in developing a more proactive approach to increase learners' attentiveness and motivation to learn the basic components in learning is the challenge that every teacher struggles in their entire years of teaching career.

The study is anchored on the tenets "Every Child is reader" (ECARP) through a DepEd Memorandum No. 402, s. 2004 and Administrative Order No. 324, which goal is to enable every Filipino child to communicate both in English and Filipino.

In response, the early grade reading assessment (EGRA) was created to provide a reliable and valid means of assessing pupils' competency in skills relevant to learning to read. The conceptual framework of EGRA is based on research on reading skill development, which has improved our understanding of the reading process.

Teachers are encouraged to utilize advanced and/or remedial reading for basic literacy and prepare pupils for advance learning and at the same time abide with the budget of work set by DepEd in the curriculum. It was also stressed that the strategy's application aims to improve students' reading comprehension of the provided materials as well as their adherence to the scheduled classes (Dita, 2016).

The public school teachers as the vanguard of education are tasked to convey to the achievement and completion of the objectives of the K to 12 curriculum which requires them to submit to the prescribed DepEd standards. They are not only required to comply with the prescribed instructional requirements but also device ways in which lessons are to be covered as budgeted and ensure that competencies are met as stated in the curriculum guide.

Teaching literacy so necessitates reading longer literary texts that demand more coverage and advance reading while maintaining the time allocated for such reading. This highlights the variety of tactics teachers use while instructing students in literature and reading. Enhancing students' reading skills, primarily in comprehension, is the main objective of these strategies.

Remedial reading was used by the teachers as a solution to issues resulting from the students' incapacity to read and understand the texts. Additionally, the intervention helps students improve their reading comprehension and skills by acting as the school's reading remediation program. This is particularly true for students whose lack of parental involvement and family support results in their reading not being reinforced at home.

Remedial reading sessions are also thought to improve students' reading comprehension of literary texts, which leads to a better learning environment. This is a result of the reading and English teachers' observations that the majority of students ignore the activity of reading literature. It has been observed that students often grow repulsed by reading literary materials rather than enjoying the study of reading and improving their reading comprehension.

However, the use of difficult and unfamiliar words in some literary materials made it challenging and demanding among Grade 2 pupils to understand the reading materials which may eventually result to disinterest of study on the part of the learners. Thus, it necessitates reading remediation or intervention to address the challenges on reading comprehension.

Reading comprehension depends on the ability to quickly sound out and recognize words, which is difficult for pupils with poor reading background and for those with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder or learning disabilities like dyslexia.

Quijano (2015) pointed out that teachers utilize the following strategies to work on developing pupils' reading comprehension skills such as improving pupils' vocabulary skills; come up with questions about the text pupils' are reading; utilize or use of context clues; looking for the main idea of the reading materials; writing a summary of what pupils' read; breaking up the reading into smaller sections; and, reading with understanding.

The study looks into the utilization of remedial reading as a strategy in teaching and developing reading comprehension and in improving pupils' reading ability. By having students deeply engage with the literary materials and drawing connections between their content and current societal challenges, remedial reading gives the teacher the opportunity to further explain the meaning of the texts. Additionally, this study will enable educators to maximize this tactic in order to enhance students' comprehension of what they read and help them deal with their reading challenges.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to evaluate a sample of Grade 2 pupils at Bonbon Elementary School in the Cagayan de Oro City Division for the academic year 2022–2023 in terms of their reading comprehension and the scope of their remedial reading program. This study specifically aimed to respond to the following queries:

1. What is the Remedial Reading Program of Teachers in select Grade 2 pupils ?
2. What is the Level of Pupils' Reading Comprehension when they are categorized as;
 - 2.1. advanced;
 - 2.2. proficient ;
 - 2.3. developing;
 - 2.4. emerging; and
 - 2.5. beginning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Pupils' Reading Comprehension and the Remedial Reading Program of Teachers in select Grade 2 pupils ?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive- correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2012) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adapted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the teachers and the Grade 2 pupils of Bonbon Elementary School, Division of Cagayan de Oro City, school year 2022-23.

There are one hundred seventy (170) Grade 2 pupils as total population, and will take only the one hundred twenty-two (122) as sample size respondents based from the computation using slovin-formula. The researcher is using scientific random sampling, specifically, unrestricted random sampling where the respondents are chosen thru lottery or table random numbers to get the sample size.

Instrument

The study used a survey questionnaire adapted from Dita (2016) who conducted a study on the effect of remedial reading on the development of reading comprehension in the public school.

The survey instrument composed of two (2) major components. The first component is the remedial reading program conducted by teachers with ten (10) indicators while the second part is on the pupils' reading comprehension levels.

Procedure

On the advice of the graduate school dean and the principal of the school, the researcher requested authorization from the superintendent

of the schools division to carry out the study.

Following that, the researcher asked the parents for permission to utilize the students' reading comprehension scores from the reading assessment used in the study.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of remedial reading program.

Problem 2 Range of scores and Percentages were used to present the reading comprehension of Grade 2 pupils.

Problem 3. Spearman-Rank Order Correlation or Spearman-Rho or Pearson -Product moment correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between level of pupils' reading comprehension and the extent of remedial reading program.

Results and Discussion

The study on remedial reading strategy: an improvement for reading comprehension among grade 2 pupils is presented, analyzed, and explained in this chapter. The data analysis and interpretation are performed using survey questionnaire responses rather than the reported difficulties.

Problem 1. What is the remedial reading program of Teachers in select Grade 2 pupils?

Teachers' remedial reading programs are essential for improving students' reading comprehension and fluency, especially for those who struggle with reading in primary school. This is because early intervention can affect how students' reading difficulties progress.

Researchers found out that remedial reading help increased connections and improved reading competence may be among the long-term benefits. Developing better communication skills and help repair pupils' speech impairments and difficulty of communicating.

Table 1. Mean Distribution of Teachers' Remedial Reading Program

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. In remedial reading teachers consistently used decoding strategies	3.90	.551	Most of the time
2. Consistently used sight word recognition techniques.	4.01	.454	Most of the time
3. Pupils consistently participate during guided reading.	4.01	.454	Most of the time
4. Teachers apply grade-level phonics and word analysis in decoding words..	3.90	.545	Most of the time
5. Teachers read grade-level text with purpose and understanding.	3.81	.607	Most of the time
6. Teachers read grade-level text orally with accuracy, appropriate rate and expression.	3.90	.545	Most of the time
7. Pupils reread a phrase to self-correct errors.	4.01	.454	Most of the time
8. Pupils self-correct close to where the error was made.	4.11	.309	Most of the time
9. Pupils use meaning, structure and visual information together to understand new words.	4.01	.454	Most of the time
10. Pupils can interpret unfamiliar words based on context.	4.01	.454	Most of the time
Overall Mean	3.97	.483	Most of the time

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/1.81-2.60 Seldom 1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1 displays the mean distribution of the extent of remedial reading program of teachers. Overall, the respondents rated the teachers' remedial reading program as "Most of the Time" with a mean of 3.96 (SD=.483). This result indicates that teachers most of the time utilized the remedial reading activities to enhance pupils' reading performance. With the use of teachers' innovative and creative reading strategies, the remedial reading program offers less proficient readers the opportunity to grow to love reading and to have experiences that will spark their interest in reading.

The remedial reading program is designed to utilize targeted instruction for pupils who have not achieved certain level of reading proficiency or learning outcomes. The reading program according to Bautista, et al (2019) focused on helping pupils to learn the specific skills that are needed to participate and learn concepts, skills, and competencies in the grade level.

Gonzales and Moncada (2020) avowed that remedial reading program helps develop pupils' ability to recognize and familiarize words and see the connections to form thoughts which develop comprehension using a self-construct knowledge through developing a purpose to keep in mind while reading and thinking about what the pupils need to know in order to understand the purpose of reading through connecting the text and the purpose of why they are reading.

The indicator, "Pupils self-correct close to where the error was made" obtained the highest mean value of 4.11 (SD=.309) which is verbally described as "most of the time". The outcome suggests that educators empower students to rectify their own mistakes, take ownership of their corrections, and actively address the issues raised by their teachers. Moreover, by working on their mistakes they will become more aware of their problems and in long term they will stop making them.

It can be deduced based on findings that remedial reading teachers are consistent in their purpose of developing pupils' ability to read proficiently through allowing them to be conscious of their errors and correct them in order to develop the level of reading competence. Therrien (2021) asserted that teachers should allow pupils to self-correct close to where the error was made in order to develop their ability to be more adept in reading words. This process or strategy allows pupils to learn comprehensively and systematically in order to achieve the desired reading fluency.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.81 (SD=.607) is verbally described as "Most of the time" in the indicator "Teachers read grade-level text with purpose and understanding". The result implies that teachers most of the time provide comprehensible text and reading materials which are appropriate to the cognition and grade-level of the remedial reading recipients. It can be inferred based on findings that teachers' provided appropriate reading materials which are coherent and intelligible to pupils' cognitive level. Espino (2020) affirmed that providing appropriate comprehensible reading materials to pupils by knowing its characteristics help enhance pupils' reading proficiency. Additionally, it was espoused that teachers' demonstration of proper reading approach helps develop and improve pupils' reading performance because it allows them to learn easily and receive more concrete, physical, and tangible reading experience.

Problem 2: What is the levels of pupils' reading comprehension when they are categorized as; Advanced, Proficient, Developing, Emerging and, Beginning?

Pupils' ability to read competently and comprehend satisfactorily are influenced by remedial reading activities of teachers, the amount of exposures to the language environment, and the quality of the reading materials as well as the reading strategies utilized by reading teachers. Researches under review asserted that pupils' reading comprehension levels are enhanced from beginning to advanced when reading-focused and interesting activities are initiated by classroom teachers. Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of pupils' reading comprehension levels categorized as advanced, proficient, developing, emerging, and beginning.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Students' Reading Comprehension Level

<i>Levels of Reading Comprehension</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Advanced	30	25%
Proficient	37	30%
Developing	28	23%
Emerging	12	10%
Beginning	15	12%
Total	122	100%

As seen, 37 (30%) of grade 2 pupils were rated "proficient" in their reading comprehension level. This finding implies that there were more pupils who performed remarkably adept in their reading comprehension based on the reading selection given. This result is attributed to teachers' ability to provide appropriate reading remediation strategies to develop and enhance pupils' reading comprehension level. Thus, it is imperative to encourage teachers to provide remedial reading activities especially during "Catch-up Friday" initiative of the Department of Education to intensify the utilization of strategies that stimulates students' reading and reading comprehension proficiency. Polinar (2019) asserted that the best way to teach reading comprehension skills among learners is to provide and create an environment where every pupil learns to read in an engaging and more motivating reading environment.

On the contrary, 12 (10%) indicates that the respondents manifest an "emerging" reading levels. This implies that only few grade 2 pupils are in the incipient reading levels. It can be deduced that pupils begin to harness an interest in reading. Pupils cannot phonically connect language to written word yet without assistance, they can comprehend that meaning is being derived within the sentences and stories they listen to. According to Barrera (2022), students who are emerging readers are able to read the alphabet and are conversant with the names, forms, and corresponding sounds of each letter. They develop Knowledge of the names of the letters and their corresponding sounds which are best predictor in developing reading. Thus, pupils with little knowledge of letters and their sounds are more likely to experience difficulties during the literacy process with obstacles to spelling, vocabulary, comprehension and reading fluency.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' remedial reading program and pupils' reading comprehension when they are categorized as: Advanced, Proficient, Developing, Emerging and, Beginning?

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the teachers' remedial reading program and pupils' reading comprehension when they are categorized as advanced, proficient, developing, emerging, and beginning.

Table 3. Test of Relationship between Pupils' Reading Comprehension and Teachers' Remedial Reading Program

<i>Reading Program</i>	<i>Pupils' Reading Comprehension</i>			
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Probability Value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision on Ho1</i>
Teachers' Remedial Reading	.002	.807	No significant relationship	Accepted

**significant at p<0.05 alpha level*

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' reading comprehension and teachers' remedial reading. Results revealed that the teachers' remedial reading program denotes "No Significant Relationship" to grade 2 pupils' reading comprehension

($r=.002$) as indicated in the probability value of .807. This result indicates that teachers' remedial reading program did not affect pupils' reading comprehension. It can be inferred based on findings that pupils' reading comprehension performance can be attributed to other factors other than teachers' remedial reading program. Torregoza (2021) asserted that pupils' reading proficiency is developed through the conduct of differentiated reading activities which develop comprehension.

Moreover, results recommended that teachers' remedial reading program denotes no significant relationship with pupils' reading comprehension. Henceforth, this present study indicated that the null hypothesis is accepted because teachers' remedial reading and pupils' reading comprehension were found to no correlation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The conduct of remedial reading is believed to help enhance pupils' reading comprehension. However, results revealed that teachers' remedial reading program do not influence pupils' reading comprehension. Development of pupils reading comprehension is influenced by other factors such as pupils' interest in reading, parental support, phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension activities.

Pupils' reading comprehension is measured based on their actual performance during the reading assessment and evaluation which are predictive teachers' ability to motivate pupils learn, teacher-learning approaches, and the amount of reading comprehension performance tasks.

There are different learning activities that may help pupils in the development of their reading comprehension skills such as the pre-reading, while reading, and after reading phases. Additionally, teachers' creativity to provide engaging reading materials promotes pupils' reading performance.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will be made aware on the reading strategies utilized by teachers and how it influences pupils' reading levels so that necessary intervention and technical assistance in developing pupils' reading competence shall be initiated such as the full implementation of the "Catch Up Friday)

School Principals/School Heads are recommended to provide support to teachers to develop their personal commitment to come up with authentic reading comprehension materials which helps promote pupils' reading competence through the conduct of the school-based learning action cell (SLAC) and other professional development program.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously develop and enhance their skills in developing and designing authentic reading materials which help them develop and intensify their reading comprehension strategies to help students improve their reading comprehension skills.

Parents are recommended to always provide the needed support in their children's learning activities and ensure parent-teachers collaboration in the education of their children. They are also enjoined to provide an inclusive support to their children's education through the provision of learner-centered home school learning environment.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders are recommended to always support and provide logistical assistance to the school especially in the utilization of information and communication technology resources which help support pupils' learning effectiveness.

Future Researchers are encouraged to carry out a similar study on the remedial reading comprehension strategies used by teachers and the reading comprehension performance of the students in order to further explore the relationships between each variable and find mitigating factors that support the growth of the students' reading comprehension capacity.

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